

Pulse radiolysis studies at NCFRR : Recent research projects[†]

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Abstract : This article is an account of the pulse radiolysis facility at the National Centre for Free Radical Research, Department of Chemistry, University of Pune and a description of the recent research work at the centre. The features and functioning of the linac system along with the issues related to its maintenance are briefly described. The pulse radiolysis studies undertaken by various groups are diverse in nature with topics ranging from antioxidants, organic sulphur systems, dyes, nucleobases, nanoparticles, metal complexes etc. and some of them are briefly reviewed.

Keywords : Pulse radiolysis, metal complex, dye, nanoparticle.

Introduction

Pulse radiolysis is an ideal technique for the generation of primary radicals of water radiolysis ($^{\bullet}\text{OH}$, $^{\bullet}\text{H}$, e^-_{aq}) and a variety of secondary radicals from them in known yields. Since the yields are well defined in dilute aqueous solutions, sparingly soluble organic and biomolecules can be easily studied. The development of instrumentation and software for data acquisition in the recent years has made the technique coupled with optical absorption detection easy for the investigation of the kinetics and absorption spectra of the transients.

Due to the high cost involved, the pulse radiolysis facilities are limited in number worldwide. In India, the linac facility at BARC, Mumbai, has been in operation during the last two decades and in order to give an impetus to the research in this area and to cater to the needs of researchers especially from the universities and other national institutes, the National Centre for Free Radical Research (NCFRR) housing the Pune University LINAC Facility (PULAF) was established by the Board of Research in Nuclear Sciences, Department of Atomic Energy. The facility has been in regular operation since three years and is being used by several researchers from BARC, universities and national laboratories.

In pulse radiolysis, a short pulse of high-energy electrons generated by an accelerator creates a significant concentration of free radicals in aqueous solutions. The major technique for the detection of the intermediate species has been absorption spectroscopy. Using this technique, radiation chemistry has witnessed an entire gamut of exciting events since its discovery half a century ago contributing not only to chemistry but to other branches of science encompassing simple to complex molecules.

Dr. J. P. Mittal has played a vital role in the establishment of this facility and this brief review describing the PULAF and highlighting the research carried out at NCFRR in the recent past is written in his honour.

PULAF : features and function

The linac can be klystron or magnetron based systems but the latter is simpler in design and less expensive. The PULAF is a 7 MeV machine powered by a magnetron and currently the facility is operational in the time domain of nanoseconds to milliseconds and a detailed account of this facility is already published^{1,2}, therefore its salient features are described here. The system utilizes a L3 (Litton) M754 grided electron gun system designed by American Science and Engineering (AS&E), USA.

[†]In honour of Professor Jai P. Mittal.

The linac is housed in a cell surrounded by three adjoining rooms housing the control unit, detection system and other utilities. The optical detection system consists of a Cermox xenon lamp (175/300 W) as a continuum source and a 5m optical fibre carries the transmitted light onto the CVI (CM-110) monochromator. The absorption traces with good signal to noise ratio were obtained using 300 W lamp. It was seen that the absorption traces of e^-_{aq} measured on pulse radiolysis of pure water using this facility are similar to that obtained using a normal pulsed xenon lamp suggesting reasonably good signals are obtained even at low intensities.

The transmitted light output was digitised with 300 MHz storage Tektronix-3230B oscilloscope interfaced to a computer for kinetic analysis. The online acquisition of kinetics and transient absorption spectra can be recorded at four different time windows using MLFP software on Labview platform. The absorption traces and the spectra at a chosen time can be viewed using the kinetic processor and super spec respectively. The absorption measurements are done using cuvette having 1 cm path length. A flow cell controlled by a peristaltic pump is used for spectral measurements and a CCTV is installed inside to view the progress of the measurements.

A selection of pulse widths ranging from 10 ns to 3 μ s is available and the machine is operated normally at 50 ns to lengthen the electron gun life. At this pulse width, typically 6–9 μ M $^{\bullet}$ OH radicals are produced in N_2O saturated solutions. The limit of detection system is 1 mOD and enables the measurement of species having low extinction coefficients ($\epsilon \sim 500 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

The facility has been in operation without any major breakdown since its regular use during the past 3 years except the recent problem encountered with a vacuum leak. The entire linac system had to be completely evacuated along with the processing of RF and the electron gun. Since a single vacuum pump is used for evacuation of the gun assembly and the linac structure, extended periods of maintenance is needed for any leak in the system. The problem may be solved to a considerable extent having separate pumps connected to each of them. In the process of restoring back the system, our technical staff gained valuable experience in troubleshooting.

Recent research activities at NCFRR

The PULAF is being used by several research groups from the University of Pune, BARC and other institutes to study the free radical chemistry of a variety of compounds which include organic, biologically important molecules and inorganic complexes. A brief account of the recent work undertaken by some of the groups is described below.

(i) Indole derivatives :

Indole and its hydroxy derivatives are biologically important molecules encountered in living organism. They are involved in many physiological functions like synthesis of vitamin B₃, neurotransmission etc. Their oxidation and their metabolites are known to cause neurodegenerative diseases. Several studies on radiation induced oxidation of 5-hydroxy indoles have been reported earlier³⁻⁶ and Dryhurst *et al.*⁷ have studied the electrochemical oxidation of indolic neurotransmitters and their metabolites, where a number of products have also been isolated and characterized. The reaction of one-electron oxidant like $Br_2^{\bullet-}$ with 5-hydroxytryptophol and tryptophol has been investigated⁶. Our recent work deals with radiation induced oxidation of several substituted indoles⁸.

The measured rate constant for the $^{\bullet}$ OH reaction with tryptamine (Tpe) in buffered solutions (pH 7) was found to be nearly diffusion controlled and remained unaffected in the pH 5–9 with $k = (6-8) \times 10^9 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. With the N_3^{\bullet} radical, the rate constant measured in neutral solution is $3.6 \times 10^9 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and is similar to that measured in acidic and basic media. The spectra measured in the $^{\bullet}$ OH and one electron oxidants, $Br_2^{\bullet-}$ and N_3^{\bullet} radical reactions in neutral solution exhibited two distinct peaks around 315–330 and 530–540 nm. No differences in the spectral features were seen in the pH range 5–9. The spectrum is assigned to indolyl radical with $\epsilon_{330} = 3300$ and $\epsilon_{530} = 2400 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The spectra recorded in the $^{\bullet}$ OH radical reaction with 5-hydroxy tryptamine (HTpe) at pH 5 have maxima at 375 and 420 nm and the decrease in absorption at lower wavelength with corresponding increase at 420 nm was seen on going to 200 μ s. However, the spectra measured in neutral and basic media did not show any such transformation and the usual bimolecular decay was seen at the two wavelengths. The 420 nm peak was attributed to

the formation of indoxyl radical by addition of $^{\bullet}\text{OH}$ followed by water elimination.

DFT calculations were performed to examine this possibility and it was shown that the (C2-OH) $^{\bullet}$ adduct of HTpe is the most stable with the overall enthalpy for addition being exothermic with $\Delta H_0 = -37.1$ and $\Delta G = -38.2$ kcal mol $^{-1}$.

An increase in absorption intensities with rising concentrations of HTpe was seen indicating dimer radical formation and the association constant for the radical adduct formation was estimated to be $4.2 \pm 0.5 \times 10^4$ dm 3 mol $^{-1}$. In contrast no such behaviour was seen in the case of Tpe indicating the lack of dimerisation.

Theoretical calculations for the dimerisation were done considering all possible structures of the radical adducts and it was concluded that the reaction mechanism involves intermolecular H transfer followed by intramolecular reorganisation through H shift resulting in stable C4-C4' and C2-C4' dimers.

The reactions of biologically important NO $_2^{\bullet}$ radical with 5-hydroxyindole (HIn), 5-hydroxytryptophol (HTpl), 5-hydroxytryptophan (HTpn) and 5-hydroxytryptamine (HTpe) was also studied using pulse radiolysis. The rate constants are much lower compared to other one electron oxidants. Our results suggest that NO $_2^{\bullet}$ radical is inefficient in oxidizing hydroxy indoles under physiological conditions resulting in toxic dimers but escape by self dimerisation and other radical reactions.

(ii) *Chalcone derivatives* :

Chalcones belong to the flavonoid family containing two phenyl rings linked by three carbon bridge and having an α,β -unsaturated ketone and are known to possess various biological activities^{9,10}. The presence of a reactive unsaturated keto function in chalcones is found to be responsible for their antimicrobial activity. A detailed investigation of radiation induced oxidation of several chalcones with a view to obtain information on their antioxidant properties is in progress. Two classes of substituted chalcones are chosen for studying the reactions of oxidizing radicals by pulse radiolysis : one group has both benzenoid rings with -OH group at 2 or 4 position while the other has an indole ring with -OH, -CH $_3$ or -NH $_2$ group at the *para* position of the phenyl ring. The $^{\bullet}\text{OH}$ radical was found to be highly reactive with chalcone derivatives with the *k* values for the three latter derivatives lying in the range $1.1-2.3 \times 10^{10}$ dm 3 mol $^{-1}$ s $^{-1}$.

Furthermore, the transient absorption spectra measured in the reaction of $^{\bullet}\text{OH}$ radical with these derivatives exhibited a peak around 390 nm. In contrast, the reaction with one electron oxidant (Br $_2^{\bullet-}$) resulted in a different spectrum having peaks around 330 and 540 nm.

(iii) *Organic sulphur compounds* :

Radiation chemical studies of aliphatic sulphides and sulphoxides have been well studied but no detailed work is reported on aromatic compounds. Highly acidic aqueous medium has been shown to be effective in generating and stabilising radical cations of aromatic systems (see Ref. 11 for a review). The $^{\bullet}\text{OH}$ radicals react by addition to the aromatic sulphides and the subsequent water elimination process leads to the formation of the radical cation in acidic media. Our recent work¹² on phenyl trifluoromethyl sulphide, a derivative of widely studied thioanisole system, has shown that very high acid concentration is required to stabilise the radical cation. Therefore the studies were very recently extended to phenyl vinyl sulphide (PVS) and phenyl vinyl sulphoxide (PVSO) and the results obtained from pulse radiolysis and theoretical calculations were recently reported¹³. The $^{\bullet}\text{OH}$ radical was found to react with both compounds by addition with $k \sim (1-2) \times 10^9$ dm 3 mol $^{-1}$ s $^{-1}$ but only the PVS-OH ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 310$ nm) adduct was entirely converted into PVS $^{\bullet+}$ at pH 1 ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 310$ and 550 nm). DFT calculations revealed that the vinylic OH adducts are in general more stable than the ring addition products and the odd electron spin in both radical cations is located over S and C atoms.

(iv) *Cytochrome P450* :

The cytochrome P450s are super families of heme-containing mono-oxygenases which carry out a vast range of oxidation reactions in nature but are very famous for their stereo and regio-specific hydroxylation reaction at unactivated C-H bond. The heme active site of all P450 enzymes contains a b-type heme with ferric iron (Fe $^{\text{III}}$) at the center which is axially ligated to a conserved cysteine thiolate and water molecule. By analogy to intermediates formed in other heme-containing enzymes such as chloperoxidase (CPO) and horse-radish peroxidase (HRP), the putative P450 oxidants are usually thought to be iron(IV)-oxo porphyrin- π -cation radical species termed compound I (Cpd I). Although the investigations about this active oxidant in P450s have been started since the initial reports of the enzymes in the 1960s but till present it remains a hot discussion. It is probably due to the transient nature and low yield of compound I, which makes

the characterization very difficult. Hence the generation of the P450 compound I species with high yield, assigning the electronic structure and the kinetic characterization still remain a great challenges.

The project pursued by the TIFR group is concerned with the study of the generation, kinetics and characterization of the reactive Cpd I species in CYP175A1, a 44-kD soluble thermostable cytochrome P450 from *Thermus thermophilus* by pulse radiolysis. The reactions are carried out by reacting hydrated electron with ferric CYP175A1 selectively by using iso-propanol to scavenge other oxidising and reducing agent such as hydroxyl and hydrogen radicals.

(v) *Dyes :*

Fenton and photo-Fenton processes are important methods of removing dyes without the generation of potentially carcinogenic aromatic amines, from wastewater produced in the textile dyeing industry before it is discharged to the environment. Pulse radiolysis can essentially contribute to the better understanding of the reaction mechanisms and hence for the development of a more efficient degradation method of pollutants. With this view, the research group at NEHU, Shillong has been carrying out a study on the kinetics and transient absorption spectra of the dye Acid Blue 161 (AB 161). The study¹⁵ involves the reactions of hydroxyl and azide radicals under different pH and at low dose rates. The rate constants with $^{\circ}\text{OH}$ radical are near diffusion controlled with $k = 2.0\text{--}2.7 \times 10^9 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the pH range 4–9 and are lower by a factor of 3 in the case of $^{\circ}\text{N}_3$ radical. Further work with two other dyes, hydroxy naphthol blue disodium salt and calmagite is under progress.

(vi) *Effect of metal ions on degradation of dyes :*

Another project deals with photostability of laser dyes which plays an important role in enhancing their fluorescence and shelf life. The project is aimed to investigate the mechanism involved in the reduction of laser dyes and the effect of metal ions during the reduction process. The preliminary pulse radiolysis data on a laser dye in the presence of silver ions has shown a fast recovery from its reduced form suggesting the protective role of the metal ion¹⁶.

(vii) *Nucleobases :*

(a) *2-Thiouracil :*

Nucleobases have been used as model systems to study the effect of radiation induced DNA because they are involved in its both oxidative and reductive damages. The radiation induced DNA damage has been studied both

by direct and indirect effects of radiolysis. The oxidative DNA damage in aqueous medium is mainly due to the indirect effect principally by the hydroxyl radical. The $^{\circ}\text{OH}$ preferentially reacts with π -bonds of nucleic acid bases, but can also interact with the sugar units by hydrogen abstraction. The previous work by the M. G. University, Kottayam related to the reactions of oxidizing and reducing radicals with nucleobases has already been published^{17,18} and their recent study is concerned with the study of reactions of $^{\circ}\text{OH}$ with 2-thiouracil (2TU), the thio analogue of the nucleic acid base uracil¹⁹.

The transient absorption spectrum obtained from the reaction of $^{\circ}\text{OH}$ with 2TU exhibited a maximum at 440 nm at pH 4.5 and the bimolecular rate constant for its formation was evaluated to be $5.2 \times 10^9 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The yield of oxidizing radicals was estimated to be 37% $^{\circ}\text{OH}$ radicals. The transient spectrum observed at pH 10.5 is blue shifted with a maximum at 350 nm. Furthermore, theoretical calculations predicted that the addition of $^{\circ}\text{OH}$ at C5 and C6 and the hydrogen abstraction from the N1 position are kinetically favoured processes. Based on theoretical calculations, the experimentally observed spectrum at pH 4.5 was assigned to (C5-OH) $^{\circ}$ while the spectrum at pH 10.5 corresponded to the N1 deprotonated adduct.

(b) *Oxidative damage of nucleobase : Effect of gold nanoparticles :*

Nanostructured materials have attracted attention in life sciences due to their potential as new analytical tool. Because of the sensitivity of nanoparticle-biomolecule complex, new nano devices for diagnostic and therapeutic purpose are being designed. Studies related to the toxicity or protective role of nanoparticles (NPs) in DNA damage are being carried out since the understanding of the mechanism is not yet clear.

One of the ongoing projects at NCFRR focuses on the role of metal NPs on DNA damage induced by ionizing radiation²⁰. It involves the study of $^{\circ}\text{OH}$ reaction with nucleobase guanine and its nucleoside dGMP in the presence of gold nanoparticles (GNPs). Being more susceptible towards oxidation, they serve as good models. Both pulse and steady state radiolysis were investigated to complement the data. Based on the data obtained in the reaction of $^{\circ}\text{OH}$ radical by pulse radiolysis and HPLC under steady state condition, the authors conclude that the GNPs seem to protect the nucleobase damage.

*(viii) Metal complexes :**(1) Ruthenium complexes :*

The research on the co-ordination chemistry of transition metal complexes having polypyridyl ligands has witnessed rapid growth in recent years as they form models for biological systems, and building blocks for supramolecular assemblies. Among them ruthenium complexes incorporating polypyridyl ligands such as phen, dppz are particularly of interest in the study of DNA interaction (see Ref. 21 for a review). Previous studies on radiation chemistry on a series of Ru^{II} complexes containing 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) and/or 6,7-dicyano dipyridoquinoxaline (dicnq) ligands provided an insight into the redox reaction mechanism²².

The same group has recently published work related to the effect on redox properties by changing phen and dicnq ligands with bpy and mebpq⁺ respectively. They have more particularly studied the reactions of oxidizing ([•]OH and [•]N₃) and reducing (e_{aq}⁻) radicals with a series of Ru^{II} polypyridyl complexes, 2,2'-bipyridine (bpy) and/or 2-(*N*-methylpyridyl)-3-pyridyl quinoxaline (mebpq⁺) having the general formula [Ru(bpy)_n(mebpq⁺)_{3-n}]⁽⁵⁻ⁿ⁾⁺ where n = 0, 1, 2 and 3. The [•]OH radical was found to react with all complexes at diffusion controlled rates with *k* values increasing from 6.2 to 9.8 × 10⁹ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ on going from [Ru(bpy)₃]Cl₂ to [Ru(mebpq⁺)₃](PF₆)₃. The rates of reaction of e_{aq}⁻ with Ru^{II} complexes are high (*k* ≈ 10¹⁰ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹) and the reaction leads to the formation of the radical anion of the bipyridine in [Ru(bpy)₃]Cl₂ and tertiary quinoxaline radical in mixed complexes containing mebpq⁺²³.

(2) Cobalt complexes :

In chemical decontamination of nuclear reactor heat transport systems, chelating agents such as EDTA and picolinic acid are used. During decontamination of nuclear reactor heat transport system, chelating agent such as EDTA and picolinic acid are used. The reactions of hydrated electron (e_{aq}⁻) and hydroxyl radical ([•]OH) with complexes of the type [Co(pic)₂(LL)], where pic = picolinate; LL = 2(H₂O), 2,2'-bipyridine (bpy), 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) and dipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine (dppz) have been carried out by pulse radiolysis²⁴⁻²⁶. The reaction of hydrated electron (e_{aq}⁻) with the above complexes resulted in the formation of ligand

radical anion species which decayed by protonation of ligand or reduction of metal via intramolecular electron transfer forming cobalt(I) species.

The reaction of other reducing radicals (CO₂^{•-} and (CH₃)₂[•]COH) gave identical species similar to that observed in e_{aq}⁻ reaction and the [•]OH radical adds to the ligand forming the OH-adduct. The decay of the transient species was also studied and the underlying reaction mechanism is discussed.

(ix) Anthracene derivatives :

Photophysical properties of 3-(9-anthrylmethyl) pentane-2,4-dione (AMPD) have been studied using techniques of steady state optical absorption, fluorescence, phosphorescence, time correlated single photon counting (TCSPC) and pulse radiolysis techniques²⁷. Fluorescence life times of AMPD were measured using TCSPC technique and give a lifetime of 7 ns in acetonitrile. The addition of triethylamine (TEA) and diethylaniline (DEA) quenches the fluorescence of AMPD. The spectra did not indicate the formation of either ground state complex or exciplex formation for both the systems. The quenching process takes place by electron transfer. Pulse radiolysis studies were carried out to obtain triplet-triplet absorption spectra of AMPD. The triplet-triplet absorption spectrum shows a peak at 460 nm and decays with a first order rate constant of ~1.2 × 10⁴ s⁻¹. The AMPD triplet does not seem to abstract H atom from 2-propanol, an H atom donor. This shows that AMPD triplet does not have enough energy for the abstraction of H atom from 2-propanol.

Conclusion

The NCFRR has been established due to the foresight and vision of Dr. J. P. Mittal with a view to cater to the needs of young researchers from the universities and national institutes and it is heartening to note that several projects using this facility are underway. We believe that the activities of the centre will be further strengthened in the years to come.

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